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RESEARCH ARTICLE

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Strategies of Learning Through The *Donkey bridge* and Singing in Early Children at Tpq Al-Ikhlas Lebakbarang

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ABSTRACT

Understanding is the result of learning from what has been read or heard, and can provide other examples that have been explained by the teacher. In the learning process, every child has different abilities. So sometimes, there are children who are left behind (understanding) from their classmates. Sometimes children feel pressured (stressed) because they are left behind from their friends. There are many cases where children don't want to study anymore because they don't go to class. Because when he doesn't go to the next class, he will most likely feel different from his friends both in terms of greater physicality and from a less intelligent level (feeling stupid). This study uses a descriptive approach, where the research aims to describe a phenomenon. Based on this theory, the researcher intends to use this approach because it can make it easier for researchers to describe the application of Learning Strategies: Easy Memorizing Through Donkey bridges and Singing in Early Childhood at Tpq Al-Ikhlas Lebakbarang. All the stimuli obtained will be material for him to learn. When the donkey bridge learning strategy is applied, the child is still a little confused about applying this concept, it takes time to explain the concept of this learning strategy. While the technique of learning by singing children is easier to apply. When taught about the material with learning strategies to sing, children will immediately understand and start humming even though they have not memorized the lyrics. From the empowerment that the author did, it was concluded that the donkey bridge strategy and singing can optimize the teaching and learning process. However, specifically, the singing strategy is easier to implement in early childhood than the donkey bridge strategy.

Keywords: Learning, Donkey Bridge, Singing, Early Children.

INTRODUCTION

The main function of the Al-Quran Education Park (TPQ) is as a place for eradicating blind reading and writing of the Koran. Indeed, Tpq also has a strategic function and role in inculcating values and characters in accordance with the values contained in the Qur'an. In the learning process, of course, there are obstacles that arise, both from the child factor, the learning process factor, and the parent factor. So we need the right strategy to increase the effectiveness of learning. Early childhood is a child with an age range of 0-6 years. This period is a time for children to grow and develop both physically and mentally, or usually referred to as the Golden Period for the development of the child's brain. (D. W. Putra, 2016) At this age, the child's intelligence development is very pressing. All the stimulation he gets will be material for him to learn.

Understanding is the result of learning from what has been read or heard, can provide other examples that have been exemplified by the teacher. In the learning process, every child has different abilities. So sometimes, there are children who are left behind (understanding) from their classmates. Sometimes children feel pressured (stressed) because they are left behind from their friends. There are many cases where children don't want to read the Koran anymore because they don't go to class. Because when he doesn't go to class, he will most likely feel different from his friends both physically and from a lower level of intelligence (feeling stupid). This empowerment aims to provide and teach Learning Strategies: Easy Memorizing Through Donkey Bridges and Singing to Early Childhood At Tpq Al-Ikhlas Lebakbarang so that it is hoped that this can encourage, motivate and raise awareness of the potential of children in accordance with the empowerment goals.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Early Childhood Psychology

According to law number 20 of 2003 concerning the national education system, it is explained that early childhood is a child with an age range of 0 to 6 years, while according to expert views, early childhood is a child aged 0 to 8 years (Sunarsih, 2007). Children are human beings with potential that needs to be developed, because this period is a golden age. At this time children are growing and developing both physically and psychologically. In addition to needing nutritious and balanced food, early childhood also needs intensive stimulants to support their growth and development. They have a distinctive character and are different from adult humans. They are active, enthusiastic, dynamic and curious about what they see, hear, feel, as if they do not stop exploring and learning from their environment. Children who receive early coaching will be able to improve their physical and mental health and well-being, which will have an impact on increasing learning achievement, work ethic, and productivity (Nurliana & Ulya, 2021). This period is a valuable year for children in understanding their environment which will have an impact on their personality, cognitive, psychomotor, and social development. All the stimulation he gets will be material for him to learn.

Cognitive Development in Early Childhood

Cognitive is the process of thinking, connecting and assessing and considering (Ambara, 2014). Cognitive development in children greatly affects their adulthood. Sociology distinguishes children into three stages, including the following:

1. The play stage is a learning process by taking the role of the people around him.
2. Game stage, is a learning process in which children, apart from knowing and understanding their own roles, also know the roles of others.
3. The generalized other stage, is in this learning process the child has been able to take on the roles that are run by other people in society and the child has also been able to interact with other people (Widodo, 2019).

Child development takes place continuously, which means that the development achieved at one stage is expected to increase both in quantity and quality at a later stage. In order to achieve optimal development, the participation of parents and adults around the environment is needed to provide stimulation to children. For children, playing activities and any activities that are concrete/real can provide a natural momentum for children to learn (Iwandana et al., 2021). This is in accordance with the development of the child's age and specific needs or individual needs. Playing is a fun and effective learning process in order to mature the development of children at pre-school age (pre-operational thinking) both from the physical and social emotional aspects.

Eduainment Learning Strategy

In essence, every child is unique, he expresses his behavior relatively and spontaneously, is active and energetic, has a strong curiosity, is enthusiastic about many things, is exploratory and has an adventurous spirit, has high fantasies but is easily frustrated, and has great attention. short. This period is period of potential learning.

Eduainment is a learning concept that is used in the world of education which is very suitable for early childhood learning, namely playing while learning. Linguistically, education comes from the

words education and entertainment. Educational is education and entertainment has the meaning of entertainment, performance and fun. So edutainment is a fun learning process. For lower-class students, fun learning is a way of learning that incorporates a basic needs-based approach. Lower-class students with traits such as a lot of moving, demanding a lot of teacher attention, and a lot of introducing new topics for students with a restricted level of concentration require more fun learning (Rahmawati, 2022).

There are four principles and characteristics of the concept of edutainment (educational entertainment) in learning, including:

1. Can bridge the learning process and the teaching process.
2. Educational learning can take place in a conducive and pleasant atmosphere through:
3. Feelings of joy can accelerate learning, while negative feelings slow down and even stop the learning process.
4. Someone who uses the potential / power of reason and emotion well will produce a leap in learning achievement.
5. The use of appropriate learning methods that can accommodate the style and uniqueness of learning, students will be able to optimize their learning.
6. Can place the child as the center and subject of education.
7. Learning with humanist principles (Purwanto, 2015).

Learning Strategies for Donkey Bridge and Singing

The factors that can cause problems in classroom management come from teachers, students, and the environment. With these problems, professional teachers must be able to overcome them (Hakim et al., 2022). The use of the donkey bridge is based on the assumption that the human brain consists of two types of memory, namely "natural" memory and "artificial memory". Natural memory is a memory in the form of talent from birth, while artificial memory is built by learning and practicing. The donkey bridge is a way to remember or memorize something that is used in education (Resmaleni, 2017). The donkey bridge is usually a word or syllable added to the word order to be memorized. The donkey bridge can be used to memorize long lists that are difficult to remember using only natural memory. The donkey bridge is a way to remember and memorize easier

The singing method is a learning process by providing one of the experiences of students by singing a song whose lyrics are in accordance with the learning material (P. Putra, 2017). Basically, children like to sing, move, and hum. Through songs, messages can be conveyed in a happy atmosphere and make it easier for children to learn.

Singing has several benefits that can be given to children, including:

1. Replace the negative atmosphere and make the atmosphere positive and calm through music and singing.
2. Sharpen children's emotions.
3. Help strengthen children's memory through interesting songs.
4. Sharpen children's imagination, appreciation, and creative abilities.
5. As a tool and media for children's learning (Feng, 2015).

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a descriptive approach, where the research aims to describe a phenomenon (Yuwanto, 2019). This research was conducted to describe the existing problems without taking into account developments at one time or periodically (Hasyim, 2016). Based on this theory, the researcher intends to use this approach because it can make it easier for researchers to describe the application of Learning Strategies: Easy Memorizing Through Donkey Bridges and Singing in Early Childhood at Tpq Al-Ikhlas Lebakbarang.

This research is a field research. In this research, it is intended to collect information by going directly to the field/target and being involved with the community being researched as well as those involved/related to the object of research (A. Aziz, 2017). about the local situation and conditions . By

conducting field research, you will be able to explore and collect data and information about the obstacles experienced during the learning process at TPQ al-Ikhlas Lebakbarang, Lebakbarang Village, Pekalongan Regency, as well as the effectiveness of the solutions offered, namely the use of donkey bridges and singing as learning strategies to make it easier for children to memorize.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research will use a donkey bridge that is used is the acrostic technique, and the singing technique. That is a technique that takes the first few letters of the word to be memorized and then assembled / put together into an interesting word/sentence so that the word order can be easily remembered. In addition, the mnemonic method or often referred to as the donkey bridge is a method that can improve memory. In addition, researchers also use the singing method which is used to help children memorize material and build a pleasant atmosphere (Ginting, 2020).

The findings of the data in the field show that there are difficulties experienced by some children in capturing the material given. This is indicated by the presence of several children who repeat the page three to eight times for one page. Children also often make mistakes and forget to answer questions when writing.

Researchers try to provide empowerment to children to increase motivation and understanding that learning is not always difficult, but can be done in a fun way . This empowerment aims to provide. Learning Strategy: Easy Memorizing Through Donkey Bridge and Singing on target. Empowerment begins with observing the object of empowerment regarding what are the obstacles for children in learning. After the observation is done, an analysis of the solutions that can be given to the child is carried out to make it easier for the child to understand the material given. In qiraati learning, learning is carried out individually and the donkey bridge strategy will only be given to children who have not been on the page for more than three volumes (Nurhasanah et al., 2018). Furthermore, the donkey bridge strategy is given together (in class) regarding the learning material provided. From these activities, it can be seen that the children feel happy and enthusiastic in receiving learning. When the donkey bridge learning strategy is applied, the child is still a little confused about applying this concept, it takes time to explain the concept of this learning strategy. can explain one to three times until the child understands the plot. In this case the author gives an example of how to memorize the letter hijaiyah ro (ر), the child is asked to connect the sound of ro with the word that is most familiar to him. Some mention bread and wheels. Then the child is asked to remember it. With it, it takes two repetitions (two days) to make the child remember the letter. While the technique of learning by singing children is easier to apply. When taught about the material with learning strategies to sing, children will immediately understand and start humming even though they have not memorized the lyrics. After memorizing the given song, the child will often repeat the song. Indirectly he has also memorized the material given without him fully realizing it. When asked to sing with them, they were very enthusiastic and began to raise their voices, spontaneous gestures or gestures also appeared such as clapping hands, ringing the table like playing a musical instrument, smiling, happy faces, and nodding their heads. From the empowerment that the author did, it was concluded that the donkey bridge strategy and singing can optimize the teaching and learning process (Rahardjo et al., 2019). However, specifically, the singing strategy is easier to implement in early childhood than the donkey bridge strategy.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research conducted, early childhood is defined as a child with an age range of zero to six years. At this age, the child's intelligence development is very pressing. All the stimulation he gets will be material for him to learn. When the donkey bridge learning strategy is applied, the child is still a little confused about applying this concept, it takes time to explain the concept of this learning strategy. While the technique of learning by singing children is easier to apply. When taught about the material with learning strategies to sing, children will immediately understand and start humming even though they have not memorized the lyrics. From the empowerment that the author did, it was

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